

CAN, COULD, MAY, MIGHT, WOULD MODAL FE'LLARINING ILTAMOS, RUXSAT, TAKLIF MA'NOLARIDA QO'LLANISHI

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada modal fe'llarini qo'llanilishi to'g'risida ma'lumotlar va misol tariqasida gaplar ham berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: can, could, may, might, would modal fe'llari.

1. Ingliz tilida iltimos qilishda can/could modal fe'llari qo'llanadi. Bunday vaziyatlar har doim hozirgi zamonda bo'lgani uchun bu yerda mazkur modal fe'llar teng ma'noda qo'llanadi. Umum qabul qilgan qoidaga ko'ra could modal fe'li can modal fe'lga qaraganda yumshoqroq ma'no beradi. Can you lend me some money? (Menga biroz pul qarzga berib turolmaysizmi?) Could you do me a favour? (Menga yordamlashib yuborolmaysizmi?) Could you open the door, please?

2. Narsa yoki buyumni so'rab olishda Can I have ... ? /Could I have ... ? /May I have ... ? qurilmalari qo'llaniladi. Bu yerda can eng norasmiy, may rasmiy ohangga ega. Can I have the salt, please?

May I have some sugar? (rasmiy)

2. Ruxsat so'rash uchun can/could/may/might modal fe'llari qo'llaniladi. Bunday vaziyatlarda ham can eng norasmiy ohangga, may/might ancha rasmiy ohangga ega hisoblanadi. Can I come in? (Tom Annadan xonaga kirishga ruxsat so'ramoqda) May I come in? (maktabda o'quvchi sinfga kirishga ruxsat so'ramoqda?

Yes, please do.

May I use your bike this evening?

Ammo ruxsat berish uchun faqat can/may modal fe'llari qo'llaniladi.

You can go home if you want.

You may smoke here. (e'lon)

3. may modal fe'li inkor shaklda taqiqni bildiradi.

You may not smoke here. (Bu yerda chekish mumkin emas.)

4. Avvaldan (umuman) ruxsat qilingan yoki ruxsat qilinmagan ish-harakatlar uchun can/can't modal fe'llari qo'llaniladi.

You can drive for a year in Britian with an international licence. (haydashingizga ruxsat bor)

You can't drive a car in Britian if you are under 17. (haydashingizga ruxsat yo'q)

5. Taklif qilishda can/would modal so'zlari qo'llaniladi.

Can I get you some water? (Sizga suv olib kelaymi?)

Can I help you ?

Would you like some coffee? (Kofe ichasizmi?)

Would you like to sit down?

Ingliz tilida modal fe'llar - asosiy fe'lga qo'shimcha ma'no yuklaydigan yordamchi fe'llardir. Masalan: can modal fe'li asosiy fe'lga qila olmoq ma'nosini qo'shadi.

I swim. (Men suzaman-modal fe'lsiz gap)

I can swim. (Men suza olaman- modal fe'lli gap)

Modal fe'llarning ko'pchiligi shaxsga qarab o'zgarmaydi. Masalan: can, could, may, might, must, should, ought to modal fe'llari shu qatorga kiradi.

I can speak five languages and he can speak five languages.

You must see the doctor and they must see the doctor.

Modal fe'llarning ko'pchiligi hozirgi zamonda fe'lning infinitiv shakli (run, read, be..) bilan to'g'ridan to'g'ri birikadi, ya'ni asosiy fe'l oldidan to qo'llanilmaydi. Masalan: can, could, may, might, must, should, needn't modal fe'llari shu fe'llar qatorga kiradi.

They may go to Italy for their holiday next week.

My grandfather could swim 3 kilometers at a time.

Ammo have to, ought to modal fe'llarida to yuklamasi mavjud.

I have to/ought to study hard for the exams.

Modal fe'llar yordamchi fe'llar bo'lganligi uchun gapni inkor qilish uchun not so'zi ularga qo'shiladi. So'roq gap hosil qilish uchun ham modal fe'llarning o'zi

qo‘llaniladi. Masalan: can, could, may, might, must, should, ought to modal fe'llari shu qatorga kiradi.

She can't even boil an egg, she is so helpless at cooking.

You shouldn't tell off the students in the presence of their parents.

Must you go so soon? You should stay a little longer.

May I come in? Yes, please do.

Ammo have to modal fe'lining so‘roq shakli va bo‘lishsiz shakllari do/does/did yordamchi fe'llari bilan yasaladi.

Do you have to get up early in the morning?

She doesn't have to buy eggs.

Why did you have to leave the party early last night?

Xulosa: Ushbu maqolada barcha modal fe'llari xaqida ma'lumotlar berilgan. Modal fe'llarining ishlatiladigan holatlariga alohida to'xtalib o'tilgan.

Foydalanish adabiyotlar:

1. Ingliz tili darsliklari
2. www.ziyonet.uz.